

Helix Nebula – The Science Cloud

Voucher Schemes for Accessing Commercial Cloud Services in the Research Environment

Abstract: Based on the experience and lessons learned from the Helix Nebula Science Cloud project, this paper identifies best practices as regards voucher schemes for accessing commercial cloud services for research purposes in Europe. Furthermore, this paper proposes recommendations for the implementation of voucher schemes in the context of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

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Introduction

The Helix Nebula Science Cloud (HNSciCloud) is a European Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) project¹ aiming at establishing a hybrid cloud platform to support the deployment of high-performance computing and big-data capabilities for scientific research. Innovative cloud services have been designed and implemented to address a set of technical challenges: compute, storage, network connectivity and federated identity management. During the last phase of the project, the two contractors developing the pilot platforms have integrated voucher schemes as a research and development (R&D) requirement of the project. Details of the pilot platforms developed by the contractors and how commercial cloud services can be integrated into the EOSC are reported in a report published by the project².

After relating the experience gathered by the HNSciCloud project in the use of voucher schemes for accessing commercial cloud services, this paper lists essential elements of a flexible and efficient voucher scheme for the research community. Finally, recommendations are made on how the implementation of voucher schemes in the EOSC could stimulate the uptake of commercial cloud services by researchers in Europe.

¹ <https://www.hnscicloud.eu/>

² Giuseppe La Rocca, & Bob Jones. (2019). D6.2 Integrating commercial cloud services into the European Open Science Cloud. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2598039>

Experience from the HNSciCloud project

Motivations

During the HNSciCloud project's pilot phase, the Buyers Group³ had access to large-scale service jointly procured from Exoscale (consortium led by RHEA) and Open Telekom Cloud (OTC) (consortium led by T-Systems). While this model fits the purpose of the ten procuring institutions of the Buyers Group, a simpler and more flexible scheme was needed to encourage uptake of the commercial cloud services by end-users. The potential advantages of a voucher scheme as an implementation of a cloud credits business model were previously explored by the PICSE and EGI-Engage projects^{4 5}. To this end, the Buyers Group requested that part of the total procured capacity be made available in the form of vouchers or cloud credits to be distributed to end-users. The procurement was performed as part of the pilot phase call-off in the context of the framework agreement established as a result of the initial tender⁶.

Buyers Group

The HNSciCloud PCP is a joint procurement carried out by 10 legal entities and the lead procurer is the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN), an intergovernmental organisation, having its seat in Geneva, Switzerland. CERN is appointed to coordinate and lead the joint PCP, and to award and sign Framework Agreements and specific contracts (the Work Orders) for all phases of the PCP, for the benefit of the following procurers, which together constitute the Buyers Group:

- European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN), Switzerland;
- Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN), Italy;
- Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (DESY), Germany;
- Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, (CNRS), France;
- Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT), Germany;
- SURFsara, the Netherlands;
- Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), United Kingdom;
- European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Germany;
- Institut de Física d'Altes Energies (IFAE), Spain ;
- European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF), France.

³ The Buyers Group includes the following organisations: CERN, CNRS, DESY, EMBL, ESRF, INFN, KIT, STFC, SurfSARA, see <https://www.hnscicloud.eu/partner-type/buyers>

⁴ Garavelli, S., Amsaghrou, R., & Jones, B. (2016, April 26). Cloud Services Procurement Roadmap for Public Research Organisations. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.50504>

⁵ Cross-border procurement of e-Infrastructure services: Opportunities, Barriers, Use cases, Best Practices, 6 March 2017, <https://documents.egi.eu/document/3013>

⁶ Christophe Veys, & Bob Jones. (2017). D2.2 Tender Material Publication. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.253998>

All members of the Buyers Group contributed to the procurement budget, the definition of the functional and procurement requirements, and participated to the award decision-making process for the contracts. Note that not all of the members of the Buyers Group were beneficiaries of the HNSciCloud grant agreement but they all signed and were bound by the HNSciCloud consortium agreement which supplemented the grant agreement to organise the procurement, the relationship between the procurers and their rights and obligations under the PCP action⁷. All members of the Buyers Group made a firm and fixed contribution to the procurement budget before the tender was launched. The sums committed by each member of the Buyers Group were not equal and their voting rights in the Procurement Collaboration Board were weighted accordingly. CERN, as lead procurer, collected 40% of their procurement commitments when the framework contracts were signed. The balance was to be paid at the end of the pilot phase but the Buyers Group preferred to pay the remaining 60% during the prototype phase. This introduced an additional step whereby the lead procurer had to reimburse the Buyers Group members' contribution to unspent procurement funds at the end of the project.

Vouchers and cloud credit schemes proposed by the Cloud Providers

To explore the use of vouchers to access commercial cloud services in the research environment, the Buyers Group requested the two HNSciCloud pilot phase consortia to develop voucher schemes as an R&D component of the project. Following this request, T-Systems and Exoscale suggested various mechanisms.

T-Systems offered three different voucher schemes:

1. Freemium model: to evaluate the OTC services, any user can register online to obtain a single voucher worth 250€⁸. This voucher can be redeemed against OTC IaaS services as a part of a new contract and expires 2 months after activation.
2. Campaign model: a funder purchases a certain amount of capacity and distributes it to end-users. The value and validity of the vouchers can be defined individually for the campaign. Each end-user must create a tenant and add a payment method in case usage would exceed the value of the voucher. As an example, a campaign was launched by T-Systems on behalf of the European Space Agency (ESA), to support ESA's Space Solution Alliance⁹.
3. Multi-project model: within a tenant, the administrator can create a number of sub-projects, and specify for each sub-project the amount of resources that may be consumed.

⁷ Details of the governance of the procurement are described in Christophe Veys, & Bob Jones. (2017). D2.2 Tender Material Publication

⁸ <https://cloud.telekom.de/en/infrastructure/open-telekom-cloud>

⁹

https://www.esa.int/Our_Activities/Space_Engineering_Technology/TTP2/Space_Solutions_Alliance_the_network_that_empowers_entrepreneurs

The Service Level Agreement (SLA) for standard use of commercial services¹⁰ applies to the voucher schemes offered by T-Systems.

Exoscale proposed a more mature voucher scheme that has already been made available to a group working on the Human Brain Project from the Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)¹¹. In this scheme, the vouchers can be prepaid or postpaid, can bear any value and have a limited or unlimited duration. Vouchers give access to all IaaS offerings with a Service Level Agreement (SLA) equivalent to a standard use of commercial services. There is no limit on the number of vouchers per tenant and usage is monitored by a monthly invoice sent by email (later replaced by an integrated report in the user interface).

Tests performed by the Buyers Group

Both cloud providers offered a small number of vouchers for test purposes to members of the Buyers Group. The initial tests were carried out by Martin Brandt, from the SURFsara institute. The following aspects were verified: account creation and the registration, possibility of redeeming vouchers under an existing tenant, limit on the number of vouchers that can be redeemed per tenant, credit usage monitoring and process once the credit is exhausted. T-Systems modified their voucher scheme taking into account feedback provided by Martin Brandt.

Based on the results of these tests, the Buyers Group concluded that both voucher schemes were sufficiently mature to be tested by end-users. For this purpose, Exoscale offered 100 vouchers and T-Systems offered 10 vouchers, all of them with a 250€ face value. The Exoscale vouchers were distributed among the Buyers Group based on the procurement budget contributions while the OTC vouchers were allocated to SURFsara.

Voucher distribution

In collaboration with CERN, the European Council for Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc¹²), identified five researchers willing to test the Exoscale voucher scheme. After reviewing the documentation available (i.e. written guidelines), two of them declined the offer due to lack of time and their concerns that they were not in a position to exploit the cloud services without local IT assistance. This highlighted a barrier to the use of commercial cloud services by end-users who do not consider themselves knowledgeable in the IT domain. A simplified user interface and comprehensive training material and documentation are therefore crucial elements to stimulate the uptake of the services by end-users with diverse backgrounds.

¹⁰ <https://cloud.telekom.de/resource/.../open-telekom-cloud-service-specifications-data.pdf>

¹¹ <https://www.humanbrainproject.eu/en/follow-hbp/news/the-human-brain-project-launches-voucher-programme/>

¹² <http://eurodoc.net/>

During the last quarter of 2018 and the first quarter of 2019, CERN distributed five Exoscale vouchers to two Eurodoc researchers. For both the organisation redeeming the vouchers (CERN) and the end-users, the process has proven to be lightweight and efficient:

- The redeeming organisation shares the voucher code(s) with the end-user (i.e. via email) and enter the end-user's email address via the Exoscale portal.
- The end-user receives an email from Exoscale with a link to create an account (tenant). Once created, the end-user enters the voucher code(s) and can immediately start using cloud services.

The two researchers reported having successfully set-up the environment within minutes and then deployed their applications, while being able to monitor the credit consumption via the dashboard. They were (very) satisfied with the Exoscale scheme and both were likely to recommend the service to colleagues.

However, the researchers expressed concerns regarding the storage of their data once their credit is exhausted. Storage of data consumes credit and hence there is a maximum delay once the credit has been exhausted for the researcher to extract their data from the commercial service and store it elsewhere. This issue impedes the uptake of commercial cloud services by end-users who do not have access to a long-term data repository. In the absence of institutional or disciplinary data repositories, catch-all or general purpose repositories do exist, such as Zenodo¹³ developed and operated by CERN as part of the European OpenAIRE project¹⁴. Zenodo offers long term sharing, curation and publication of data, software and other digital artefacts. Content may be uploaded free of charge within defined volume and size limitations¹⁵.

It is possible to interface commercial cloud services with Zenodo in order to overcome the issue of long-term data storage. An example application that loads data from Zenodo, processes it and deposits the results back into Zenodo has been made available by CERN.

¹³ <https://zenodo.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

¹⁵ <http://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

Voucher Schemes: Best Practices

During the HNSciCloud project, the Buyers Group identified crucial elements that must be integrated in a voucher scheme for it to be attractive to research organisations and end-users. These elements are summarized as a checklist in this section.

A fixed value in monetary units

The value of a voucher shall be fixed and defined in monetary units, preferably Euros. The value must be in monetary units rather than service specific units (i.e. CPU-hours, GB-hours, etc.) to give the end-user flexibility in choosing the type of services that matches their research needs.

Free at the point of use

The end-user should not be required by the cloud service provider to provide an additional payment method in case of overspending (see point on data repatriation policy and associated costs for more details).

Defined duration of validity

The cloud provider and the organisation buying vouchers must agree on a duration of validity, ideally one year or more. It is important to specify whether the duration of validity starts when the vouchers are purchased by the organisation or activated by the end-user. Ideally, the voucher duration should be displayed on the user interface.

No limitation on the number of vouchers that can be consumed by a tenant

An organisation buying vouchers from a commercial cloud provider must be able to distribute them to end-users whether they have an existing account (tenant) or not. The obligation to create a new tenant for each voucher would cause a discontinuity in the research process for end-users.

Defined catalogue of services

The types of services that can be accessed with vouchers must be clearly specified and visible via an online catalogue. Ideally, it should be possible for an end-user to filter the set of visible services in the catalogue against which a voucher can be redeemed. In addition, the cost of the different services must be visible. Cloud service price calculators for different configuration are appreciated by end-users in order for them to perform financial planning of their use of their services.

Up-to-date and detailed documentation and tutorials

It is the responsibility of the cloud provider to provide comprehensive and up-to-date documentation. Preferably, the documentation is layered in several levels of complexity to address the different user profiles and backgrounds. Tutorial videos are appreciated by non-technical end-users while detailed written guidelines are suitable for more proficient end-users. Such material will encourage end-users without strong technical knowledge to use the services. Consultancy on the deployment of applications could itself be a separate service purchased with vouchers.

Near real-time usage monitoring

Both the end-users and the organisation buying vouchers shall have access to a near real-time consumption monitoring tool, preferably directly via the user interface. In addition, cloud providers shall provide the procuring organisation with regular overview reports on the types and scale of services consumed by end-users via redeemed vouchers.

Applicable Service Level Agreement (SLA)

The cloud provider and the organisation buying vouchers shall agree on an SLA and on compensations applicable in case of breach of this agreement. The SLA shall specify the dispute resolution process in case the desired services are not available to the voucher user. Support channels for communicating with the service provider as well as a ticketing system should be specified in the SLA. Ideally, the SLA should address all the aspects identified in the ISO/IEC 19086 standard¹⁶.

Clear data repatriation policy and associated costs

The cloud provider is responsible for warning the end-user when their credit is about to be exhausted. The end-user should be given the option to:

- topping-up the credit with another voucher or other payment means in order to continue using the services
- or backing-up the data locally and stop using the service

The cloud provider is responsible for stopping the running instances once the credit is exhausted and preventing the end-user from creating new ones. If the end-user did not repatriate the data before the credit is exhausted, s/he should be given the possibility to do so by using a new voucher. The period during which the data is kept by the cloud provider after a user has exhausted his/her credit shall be agreed in the SLA.

¹⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/67545.html>

Implications for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

As stated in the publication “Prompting an EOSC in practice”¹⁷, euro-denominated EOSC vouchers are to be investigated as a mechanism to grant access to researchers to cloud resources within the EOSC. For this option to be viable, the following aspects should be considered.

Multi-cloud vouchers and associated business model

In the context of the EOSC, several cloud providers will offer vouchers. This has implications both for the funding agencies and the service providers. In HNSciCloud, vouchers were pre-paid and linked to an individual supplier. This implies the procurer has to estimate the number of vouchers to be procured and risks to have procured but unused vouchers at the end of the scheme. More general voucher schemes, with vouchers valid for multiple suppliers, are possible but have implications for the cash-flow of the suppliers. We suggest that, for the sake of simplicity and engagement of suppliers, pre-paid vouchers for each participating service supplier are used as an initial implementation for EOSC.

The freemium model, offered by many cloud providers such as Amazon Web Services (AWS)¹⁸ and Google Cloud¹⁹, may contribute to the definition of the EOSC voucher scheme. However, since the freemium models of the suppliers are discretionary and can be withdrawn at any time, a procurement based contract is preferred to ensure the voucher scheme is available during a defined timeline to all researchers that the procuring organisation(s) wish to support.

An activity worthy of mention is the recently announced EO-AWS EO Cloud Credits Programme²⁰ which offers GEO Member agencies and research organizations from developing countries access to free cloud services to help with the hosting, processing and analysis of big data about the Earth to inform decisions for sustainable development.

Catalogue of services

EOSC is establishing a marketplace of services to be made available to researchers via the portal²¹, some of which could be accessible with vouchers. Based on experience gathered

¹⁷ Prompting an EOSC in practice - Final report and recommendations of the Commission 2nd High Level Expert Group on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), European Commission, 2018, DOI 10.2777/112658

¹⁸ https://aws.amazon.com/free/?sc_icontent=awssm-evergreen-free_tier&sc_iplace=2up&trk=ha_awssm-evergreen-free_tier&sc_ichannel=ha&sc_icampaign=evergreen-free_tier

¹⁹ <https://cloud.google.com/developers/startups/>

²⁰ <http://www.earthobservations.org/article.php?id=345>

²¹ EOSC Marketplace <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/>

in the HNSciCloud pilot phase, data is only part of the information that needs to be migrated when moving between services. User-specific information, such as profiles, custom VM images and applications etc. should also be transferred when switching between services. As highlighted in the HNSciCloud report 'Integrating commercial cloud services into the European Open Science Cloud', in the context of the free flow of non-personal data Regulation, the European Commission has encouraged the development on a self-regulatory basis of a Code of Conduct for Cloud Switching/Data Porting (SWIPO). In anticipation of this regulation, SWIPO has been formed as the collective name of a group of stakeholders that are working towards a code of conduct in the domain of Cloud Computing. Such a code of conduct should be taken into account for the EOSC Rules of Participation²² for service providers.

Long term data storage

The storage of the research data generated on cloud services accessed with vouchers is a concern for researchers and might hamper the use of vouchers. Consequently, the EOSC must propose long term data storage solution(s) that can be combined with the vouchers. For EOSC voucher recipients without access to an institutional or disciplinary data repository, CERN proposes to enable access to the Zenodo open-access repository.

Compatibility with Data Management Plans (DMPs)

The incompatibility of the IT services accessed via vouchers and the researchers' DMPs is a clear barrier to adoption. On one hand, researchers are not likely to modify a study protocol to ensure it authorizes the use of new IT services as this operation is time consuming and costly. On the other hand, research funding agencies have different requirements for DMPs, some make suggestions on repositories where data is to be deposited (e.g. European Research Council²³) but do not give guidance on processing, while others (e.g. UK's Medical Research Council²⁴) request the applicant to identify formal information and data standards with which their study will be compliant.

Compliance with DMP requirements is not an issue for the voucher scheme itself but rather the cloud services that are accessed via the vouchers. Consequently, the EOSC must consider how the services in its catalogue will address the issue of compliance with DMP

²² EOSC Rules of Participation <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/governance/rules-participation>

²³ https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/file/ERC_info_document_Open_Research_Data_and_Data_Management_Plans.pdf

²⁴ MRC Template for a Data Management Plan, v01-1, 10 March 2017, <https://mrc.ukri.org/documents/doc/data-management-plan-template>

requirements²⁵. Science Europe highlighted this issue in their guide 'Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management'²⁶ which states:

Currently, there is a lot of variation in research data management policies. Many research funding organisations, research organisations, and research communities have developed their own rules and templates. This can be confusing for researchers and is especially problematic as many researchers acquire their funding from different sources; they are increasingly confronted with different grant requirements and institutional policies. There is an urgent need to align data management policies in order to provide more clarity for researchers. DMPs should not be a bureaucratic burden for them, but a useful means of support when planning and conducting a research project.

²⁵ https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/file/ERC_info_document-Open_Research_Data_and_Data_Management_Plans.pdf

²⁶ 'Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management': D/2018/13.324/4, Science Europe, November 2018, <http://scieur.org/rdm-guide>

Future work

The EGI Applications on Demand (AoD) service²⁷ is being interfaced, via EC3 in the context of the EOSC-Hub project²⁸, to Exoscale IaaS services so that HNSciCloud vouchers can be used to execute applications and application-development and hosting frameworks, such as NAMD, Galaxy, Octave, Docker, Hadoop, Apache, Gnuplot and R, that support compute-intensive data analysis.

Vouchers could also be used as a means of implementing compensation to procurers by service providers when the terms of an SLA are breached. For example, in the scenario when a service is unavailable for a period that extends beyond the duration specified in the SLA. This usage of vouchers was also successfully tested during the pilot phase of the HNSciCloud project but implies an agreed method for monitoring SLA breaches between procurers and cloud service providers.

Conclusion

Thanks to the HNSciCloud project, experience in the use of vouchers to access commercial cloud services was gathered. Voucher schemes have proven to be a flexible and efficient way of stimulating the uptake of commercial cloud services by end-users. Lessons learned from this project show that a set of elements must be integrated in a voucher scheme in order to make it attractive both to the organisation purchasing vouchers and to the end-users that redeem them.

This paper supports the idea of using vouchers in the EOSC to encourage researchers to test new services and new infrastructures at a small scale for a limited duration. Vouchers are an effective mechanism to encourage new procurers to make use of cloud services. Vouchers are also an effective mechanism for procuring organisations of any size to support test and development activities involving cutting-edge architectures and services without impacting their production environments. However, vouchers are probably not the most appropriate procurement mechanism for well-planned, continuous or large scale usage and for use cases with demanding storage and network requirements.

To ensure the sustainability of the scheme, we recommend that the EOSC governance structure defines a set of minimum requirements for cloud providers willing to participate to the EOSC using the voucher scheme, potentially as part of the Rules of Participation²⁹ and include an Acceptable Usage Policy³⁰ for the voucher recipient.

²⁷ <https://marketplace.egi.eu/42-applications-on-demand-beta>

²⁸ <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/>

²⁹ EOSC Rules of Participation <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/governance/rules-participation>

³⁰ Acceptable Usage Policy https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Acceptable_use_policy

Elements from the best practices summarized in section two of this paper should be taken into account when defining the voucher scheme. If such a voucher scheme proves successful, its expansion will need to take into account the potential brokerage roles within the cloud services market as described in the CloudWatch2 project report³¹.

³¹ Roadmap to a cloud market structure encouraging transparent cloud pricing, Final iteration - September 2017, <http://www.cloudwatchhub.eu/Roadmap-for-transparent-pricing>